

Synthetic Biology and the Future of Global Environmental Governance

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Florian Rabitz^{1 2 3}

Abstract

Synthetic biology is a fast-moving technological field that combines novel forms of genetic engineering with digital technologies, machine learning, and artificial intelligence. Some hail it as a potential solution for pressing challenges of environmental sustainability, for instance by providing powerful tools that could neutralize biological threats to species and ecosystems. Others stress potential environmental risks associated with releases of novel synthetic organisms. The technology also raises complex social and political questions, including on equity, participation, as well as risk assessment and management. This GGI Analysis provides a broad overview of the state of the discussion, focusing on two principal areas: a) the fusion between synthetic biology and Artificial Intelligence, whereby Large Language Models are presently being trained on genetic sequence data, including for the potential design of novel synthetic organisms; and b) the use of synthetic biology for controlling biological threats such as invasive alien species or animal pathogens with human pandemic potential. The report surveys current international governance responses under the Convention on Biological Diversity and its Cartagena Protocol on Biosafety, and develops some preliminary parameters for the long-term governance of synthetic biology.

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1. Introduction

The life sciences have undergone profound shifts in the past two decades (Benner and Sismour 2005; Church et al. 2014). The development of new techniques for gene editing, notably CRISPR/Cas9, has led to the widespread adoption of cost-effective and easily accessible tools for high-precision genetic engineering. Gene editing has rapidly become a staple technology in fields such as agricultural biotechnology, where it now allows gene insertion and removal, as well as regulation of gene expression, at a level and with an accuracy that goes far beyond what previous transgenic plant breeding techniques allowed (Schaart et al. 2016). Advances in genetic sequencing technology have reduced the costs of mapping out entire genomes from prohibitive to marginal (Shendure et al. 2017). Digitalization has then enabled the creation of vast databases that can contain hundreds of millions of genetic sequences. Machine learning techniques now allow researchers to comb through those databases to identify hereditary diseases, to pinpoint genes that might be of interest for specific commercial applications, or to facilitate rapid vaccine development for responding to viral pandemic threats. Researchers have synthesized life in the laboratory - living micro-organisms derived from inorganic components. A group of techniques known as *directed evolution* mimics natural selection pressure for protein design. Researchers are exploring the reversal of molecular chirality, that is, the right-handedness of

nucleotides and the left-handedness of amino acids, which could lead to “mirror organisms” that “would constitute a radical departure from known life” (Adamala et al. 2024: 1351). And whereas all natural life on the planet is based on only five different nucleotides, molecules that jointly form the DNA or RNA polymers that carry the genetic blueprints of life, researchers have now developed XNA – Xeno Nucleic Acids incorporating nucleotides that do not exist in nature.

All these and other developments are usually subsumed under the label of “synthetic biology” - an umbrella term that refers to a wide range of techniques, applications, and products of contemporary biotechnology. It is not easy to define, and it is equally challenging to draw a clear conceptual boundary between synthetic biology and other contemporary biotechnologies. What complicates the matter further is that, for some, synthetic biology refers to a rather narrow set of specific applications, or specific types of genetically modified organisms (GMOs) whereas, for others, it is largely synonymous with biotechnology as such. Somewhere in the middle are those observers who consider synthetic biology as a field that fuses new biotechnologies with digital technologies, particularly big data analytics, machine learning, and artificial intelligence (AI).⁴

These conceptual and definitional issues are vexing. A common starting point is the definition adopted by the 193 parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), the central international forum for deliberations on

⁴ For further reading, see Church et al. 2014; Carbonell et al. 2019; CBD 2022a.

synthetic biology for more than a decade. In its decision XIII/17, the CBD's Conference of the Parties understands synthetic biology as "a further development and new dimension of modern biotechnology that combines science, technology and engineering to facilitate and accelerate the understanding, design, redesign, manufacture and/or modification of genetic materials, living organisms and biological systems" (CBD 2016). It is in the nature of such decisions to reflect careful diplomatic compromises, and the decision text crucially remains uncommitted whether synthetic biology is a marginal improvement on existing techniques and applications; or whether it presents a new and distinct paradigm of its own.

Synthetic biology has considerable practical, potential, as well as hypothetical implications for a broad range of political issue areas (e.g. Roell and Zurbruggen 2020; Voigt 2020). This includes the realm of biosecurity, where the dual-use aspects of synthetic biology have prompted considerable anxiety in the past decade over various forms of do-it-yourself bioterrorism, and about its potential role in clandestine offensive bioweapons programs of nation states (Brent et al. 2024). Another area where synthetic biology has garnered significant interest in the past years, and which is the focus of this text, is in the domain of environmental sustainability. In principle, synthetic biology could offer a variety of ways for responding to various catastrophic processes of environmental change that we are presently witnessing, from climate change to extinction-level biodiversity loss (Piaggio et al. 2017). Synthetic biology could offer ways of

counteracting biological threats to sustainable development, be it invasive alien species in vulnerable island ecosystems in the Pacific region (Leitschuh et al. 2018) or plant pathogens that threaten agrifood systems in Sub-Saharan Africa. New types of genetically modified plants and trees could sequester unusually large amounts of carbon and thus contribute towards the balance between greenhouse gas emissions by sources, and their removals by sinks, that the 2015 Paris Agreement prominently foresees for the second half of this century (e.g. Jatain et al. 2021). Species once believed to have been lost due to anthropogenic interference need not necessarily remain so, as a wide scientific discussion on the re-creation of extinct species, so-called de-extinction, attests to (Shapiro 2017). On the flipside, synthetic biology implies numerous novel risks. These may be environmental in type and for instance relate to the harmful and irreversible potential impacts of proposed methods for large-scale, ecosystem-level genetic engineering (Rabitz 2022; Frieß et al. 2023). There may also be socio-economic risks, as synthetic biology may entail novel practices of misappropriating biological materials that are in the custody of nation states or local communities (Rabitz 2015; Nehring 2022).

This GGI Analysis provides a panoramic overview and analysis of the (potential) role of synthetic biology in global environmental governance. The perspective developed here is open-ended regarding the ultimate desirability of various applications of synthetic biology, as well as their respective risk-benefit ratios. As will be argued, however, there is a need for

accelerated international rule development to ensure proper capture of benefits, and proper management of risks. International environmental law provides several overarching principles with intrinsic relevance to synthetic biology, particularly concerning environmental releases. This is, most notably, the precautionary principle which urges restraint when dealing with complex technological risks. International environmental law also provides various specific regulatory frameworks, notably on biosafety and on access to and benefit-sharing from genetic resources, that bear high relevance for synthetic biology but require considerable adjustment before being able to provide operational rules. Thus, this GGI Analysis also outlines proposals for future-proofing the international biodiversity- and biosafety regimes in the face of fast-moving technological changes in the life sciences. There are no easy answers, but the international community of scientists and policy-makers need to come up with them quickly.

Parts 2 and 3 of this GGI Analysis examines two specific fields of application of synthetic biology, focusing on its (potential) environmental impacts, but also different socio-ecological considerations worth bearing in mind for critically assessing the benefits and risks of this technology. Part 2 discusses the recent fusion between synthetic biology and generative AI. Research in synthetic biology increasingly deploys Large Language Models (LLMs) trained on vast genetic sequence databases. This raises questions of ownership, control, and benefit-sharing, as well as questions related to biosafety. Part 3 turns to the

field of genetic biocontrol: The (proposed) use of various types of genetic interventions for counteracting biological threats to sustainable development, from invasive alien species to animal pathogens. Part 4 surveys the international politics of synthetic biology. While numerous international forums have begun addressing the issue in recent years, the CBD, its Cartagena Protocol on Biosafety, and (partially) its Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit-sharing, are the primary international instruments currently handling synthetic biology, subject to protracted and contentious political processes. Part 5 develops parameters for the forward-looking governance of synthetic biology: Even if we do not currently know where international regulation might need to end up, it is possible to identify procedural elements that would facilitate the international political process. The GGI Analysis concludes with concrete policy recommendations for the future of global governance of synthetic biology.

2. Generative AI and digital sequence information

The genetic code that underpins all forms of biological diversity is increasingly stored in genetic sequence databases. DNA sequencing used to be prohibitively expensive. With close to a 3 billion US\$ price tag, the Human Genome Project, which mapped the entire human genome between 1990 and 2003, was one of the largest and most expensive scientific enterprises in

history. By 2017, a single researcher operating equipment worth a few thousand US\$ was able to sequence 40 times the volume of the entire Human Genome Project in just two days (Shendure et al. 2017). Today, sequencing costs are more than 1 million times lower than during the 1990s (Uhlen and Quake 2023). The volume of data that is being generated in this way is staggering. As of 2025, the European Nucleotide Archive contains 5.4 billion different DNA sequences amounting to 30.7 trillion bases. GenBank, a database under the US National Institutes of Health, contains data of 250 million genomes. A database jointly operated by the Food and Agriculture Organization and the International Atomic Energy Agency, on plant mutants containing potentially relevant traits for breeding, covers hundreds of varieties of rice, barley, wheat, or soybean. Other specialized databases list sequence data for everything from influenza viruses to human genetic diseases.

Such data has been used in a wide range of commercial and non-commercial activities for a long time. However, the development and rapid uptake of LLMs in the past few years is currently changing the scientific, commercial, and regulatory landscape in ways that are likely unprecedented. LLMs, for most purposes meaning the Generative Pre-trained Transformers that were popularized with the release of ChatGPT in 2022, are machine learning algorithms trained on vast amounts of data. Just as they can be trained on natural language, it is possible to feed them genetic sequence data. AlphaFold, an AI model that can predict protein structure from amino acid sequences, thus solving a

perennial problem that had haunted modern biology for decades, was trained on protein data stored in a public repository (Jumper et al. 2021). AlphaFold has revolutionized protein design in the past few years and is being rapidly adopted for commercial applications. Genome-Scale Language Models trained on millions of prokaryotic gene sequences have been used to predict the evolutionary dynamics of the SARS-CoV-2 virus (Zvyagin et al. 2023). With vast commercial potential, the development of genomic LLMs is now being spearheaded by industry giants such as NVIDIA, Meta, and Alphabet. Yet as commercial interest rises, the political stakes are increasing as well.

Digital sequence information

For one, the utilization of genetic materials has long been linked to the question of resource mobilization for biodiversity conservation. The 1992 CBD created a regulatory framework for so-called Access and Benefit-Sharing (ABS) that revolves around bilateral agreements between providers of genetic resources (e.g. nation states or local communities) and users (e.g. commercial users from the pharmaceuticals or plant breeding sectors, but also non-commercial public researchers; see Buck and Hamilton 2011). ABS arrangements have proliferated under international law since then (Rabitz 2017). Similar arrangements now exist for agricultural genetic resources under the UN Food and Agriculture Organization; for certain types of viruses under the World Health Organization; and for marine genetic resources under the 2023

Agreement on Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction (BBNJ Agreement). Thus, international law has widely codified the idea that the utilization of genetic resources needs to be linked to legal and institutional arrangements that would allow the fair and equitable sharing of the derived benefits, which may include commercial profits (see Morgera and Tsioumani 2010).

For more than a decade, policy-makers have struggled with the implications of digitalization on international ABS arrangements (see Halewood et al. 2023). In general, the relevant international agreements only apply to physical samples, but not to their digital representations. Article 2 of the CBD, for instance, defines genetic resources as “any material of plant, animal, microbial or other origin containing functional units of heredity” that is “of actual or potential value“. Yet digital sequence information do not constitute “material”, and neither do they contain “functional units of heredity“. As biotechnological research and development has been shifting from physical samples to digital representations, international ABS regimes have started to drift into irrelevance. Only recently have policymakers found answers to the challenge of ABS and digital sequence information. Article 9 of the 2023 BBNJ Agreement expressly provides for fair and equitable benefit-sharing from activities related to marine genetic resources and associated digital sequence information. In 2024, the CBD’s 16th Conference of the Parties established a new multilateral mechanism that encourages large commercial users of digital sequence information to pay into a multilateral

fund that would, in turn, finance projects related to the conservation of biological diversity (CBD 2024a).

These developments come at a time when Big Tech players have already requisitioned considerable shares of public genetic databases for training their next-generation AI models. This unlocks potentially significant commercial gains, parts of which could reasonably be channeled towards conservation, considering that the very existence of these AI models presupposes sufficient biodiversity for providing training data. Using annual profits of tech giants such as NVIDIA or Meta as a benchmark, the potential for resource mobilization is considerable. This will, however, largely depend on the implementation of the BBNJ Agreement and the CBD’s Multilateral Mechanism in jurisdictions with strong commercial activity. As the US is neither a party to the CBD nor to the BBNJ Agreement, the future regulation of digital sequence information in the training of AI models depends crucially on what the European Union will do. In addition, there is likely a need to resolve outstanding issues related to intellectual property, as some public gene databases do not allow the unfettered commercialization of the data they host. As LLMs are largely black boxes, however, it is practically difficult or even impossible to prove which kinds of digital sequence information, from which sources and with which legal strings attached, have been used in the training of any given model. The regulatory challenges for leveraging genomic LLMs for biodiversity conservation are, in other words, enormous.

Biosafety

Genomic LLMs pose very specific biosafety challenges. Most jurisdictions have in place some form of mandatory risk assessment prior to the environmental release of GMOs with uncertain properties and environmental implications. In the European Union, this is based on the 2001 Deliberate Release directive (2001/18/EC). There, GMO risk assessment generally proceeds in several steps: identification and characterization of hazards (i.e. potential adverse effects associated with specific GMOs); exposure assessment (i.e. the calculation of the probability with which humans or the environment could be exposed to hazards); and risk characterization (i.e. a quantitative or qualitative estimate of probability and harmfulness of adverse effects). A key principle is the use of comparators. For instance, non-modified crops that are proven to be safe for human consumption can serve as a benchmark for assessing the risk of transgenic varieties. A type of potato that has not undergone genetic modification could provide a template for evaluating a modified potato of the same type.

Decades of experience exist in applying this overall approach to GMOs where the nature and purpose of genetic modifications are known. But this is not necessarily the case for GMOs designed by genomic LLMs. Users could prompt LLMs to generate genetic sequences for organisms that possess specific traits, say, an oil-eating bacterium for environmental remediation. Yet users are not necessarily in a position to comprehend the reasoning that informs model output. Even more, hallucinations

currently appear to be an intrinsic feature of LLMs. This is unproblematic if it makes an LLM produce images in which members of the British royal family have eleven fingers instead of ten. It might be a more serious issue when designing custom-tailored GMOs intended for environmental release. Genetic hallucinations might have unpredictable (and undesirable) consequences. As users may not fully understand the inner workings of the model, the risks associated with those GMOs could be difficult to assess prior to their release.

3. Genetic biocontrol

A considerable amount of research is presently going into methods for controlling biological threats to sustainable development through genetic interventions. Such threats may be of different kinds. For one, invasive alien species are one of the most formidable direct drivers of global biodiversity loss. They can include rodents introduced into vulnerable island ecosystems via transport or tourism; aquatic micro-organisms that are shipped halfway around the globe in the ballast water of container ships; or Chinese muntjacs, small deer that have become invasive in the UK after escaping from a private zoo. A recent assessment by the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services summarizes that “[m]ore than 37,000 established alien species have been introduced by human activities across all regions and biomes of Earth, with new alien species presently being recorded at an unprecedented rate of approximately

200 annually” (Roy et al. 2023: 12). Effective protection of global biodiversity requires getting the problem of biological invasions under control. This same applies for plant pests, whether invasive or otherwise. In some developing countries, pests such as the Fall armyworm can endanger up to a third of agricultural production. This makes them a major threat to food security and agricultural biodiversity. Finally, genetic vector control is also being explored at the intersection of biodiversity and public health. Numerous infectious diseases that primarily occur in developing countries are carried by insect vectors. Where vaccines are unavailable, targeting the vectors offers a possibility for reducing public health burdens. Such vector control can take on a variety of forms, and toxic chemicals such as DDT have been (and, in some regions, continue to be) used for their insecticidal properties (see Wilson et al. 2020). However, genetic vector control is increasingly being explored as an alternative route.

The following subsections outline three systems for genetic biocontrol that partially differ in purpose and are presently at different stages of development. Each of those touch on definitional issues mentioned in the introduction: While some or all of them are considered to fall into the category of synthetic biology by at least some stakeholders, others might classify them differently.

The first of these, the most well-known one, are gene drive systems. These are genetic modifications that bias inheritance rates and thus make it more likely that specific genes are inherited during sexual reproduction (see Bier 2022). Over time, the frequency with

which the targeted gene occurs in a natural population thus increases exponentially. In species that reproduce on a scale of days or weeks, gene drive systems can effectively re-write the genetic code of entire populations occurring in a given geographic region and possibly beyond. An initially limited release of small numbers of drive carriers would, over the course of months or a few years, cause large-scale genetic modification. This would allow human operators either to *replace* natural populations of species with genetically-modified ones; or to *suppress* them, by reducing biological fitness or through infertility genes. Gene drives are primarily being explored for disease vector control, but also for combating biological invasions in vulnerable island ecosystems (Leitschuh et al. 2018).

A second system for genetic biocontrol, and one that is significantly less advanced along the research and development pipeline, are self-spreading viruses. These are, in a nutshell, infectious organisms that are released into the wild, for instance to trigger immune responses in target species, thus conferring immunity against specific pathogens. This technique is being explored as a tool against pathogen spillovers into human populations. Potential areas of application include Lassa fever or rabies, but also global pandemic threats that emerge out of animal reservoirs (Nusmer et al. 2020). Agricultural applications, where self-spreading viruses act as insecticides, are being explored as well (Lentzos et al. 2022). As with other applications discussed here, the biosafety challenges are considerable, as genetically modified viral biocontrol

agents may persist in the environment, making any release, whether intentional or unintentional, potentially irreversible (Henderson and Murphy 2007).

The third and final system is the most complex one. Horizontal Environmental Genetic Alteration Agents (HEGAAs) have been explored by the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency, the R&D division of the US military, for purposes of biodefense. HEEGAs are tripartite systems, where genetically modified insects deliver genetically modified viruses to crops in the field to carry out genetic modifications *in situ*. Specifically, the viruses would introduce novel traits into the crops that could immediately engineer resilience to natural hazards or reverse the impacts of a biological attack targeting agrifood systems (Pfeifer et al. 2022). The nature of this research is distinctly dual use, and comes dangerously close to infringing on the unequivocal, categorical prohibition of offensive bioweapons programs under international law (see Reeves et al. 2018).

In principle, these and other novel biocontrol methods could provide powerful instruments for combating sustainability challenges from biodiversity loss over food insecurity up to vector diseases. At the same time, they pose numerous complicated challenges (Rabitz 2024a). As they would constitute the first time that genetic engineering is carried out directly in the field, and not in the laboratory, risk assessment is demanding. Moreover, the nature of these interventions makes them prone to transboundary movement. This increases the political stakes: In

principle, governments have the right to restrict, or prohibit, transboundary movements of potentially harmful GMOs into their territories. In practice, cross-border flows may be impossible to prevent or even detect. For instance, a hypothetical environmental release of gene drive systems for combating Malaria transmissions in Burkina Faso might easily spill over into Mali, Benin, or Togo, as the geographical range of mosquitoes rarely corresponds to the geography of political borders. Transboundary movements are especially problematic if novel biocontrol agents cause harmful environmental effects and become a matter of liability and redress under international law. Thus, while interest in genetic biocontrol is partially a response to the failure of conventional policy instruments in dealing with sustainability challenges such as invasive species or vector-borne diseases, their environmental risks and political implications make them extraordinarily controversial.

4. The global governance of synthetic biology

The primary global forum for the complex and contentious politics of synthetic biology is the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD). The CBD emerged out of the 1992 UN Conference on Environment and Development as one of the three Rio Conventions, together with the Framework Convention on Climate Change and the Convention to Combat Desertification. The CBD has presently

196 parties, including the European Union, but excluding the US. It has always been more than a pure nature-protection instrument. From its very beginning, the CBD has had a strong technological focus due to the many ways in which biodiversity policy interfaces with modern biotechnology. This focus is powerfully highlighted by the fact that the CBD's three protocols all deal with technological matters: The 2000 Cartagena Protocol on Biosafety addresses the safe use, handling, and transfer of Living Modified Organisms (LMOs; CBD nomenclature largely equivalent with GMOs). The 2010 Nagoya-Kuala Lumpur Supplementary Protocol creates a mechanism for liability and redress in association with environmental harm caused by LMOs. Finally, the 2010 Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit-Sharing provides monitoring- and compliance mechanisms for implementing one of the CBD's three objectives, the fair and equitable sharing of the benefits arising out of the (biotechnological) utilization of genetic resources. Traditionally, the political geography of the CBD has closely tracked a North-South divide which, particularly on biotechnological issues, is increasingly giving way to more complex configurations of bargaining coalitions. The CBD is also widely perceived as an anti-technology forum due to its strong institutionalization of the precautionary principle, and arguably also due to the institutional access of critical, anti-technology, and / or anti-capitalist Nongovernmental Organizations (NGOs).

The CBD has been grappling with synthetic biology since at least 2010. Back then, discussions began whether synthetic biology should formally be

classified as a new and emerging issue, which would make it a permanent agenda item for the CBD's Subsidiary Body on Scientific, Technical, and Technological Advice (SBSTTA; CBD 2010). 15 years later, this seemingly minor procedural issue remains unresolved (CBD 2022b). The background to this is that several parties to the CBD oppose a precautionary framing of synthetic biology that emphasizes risks over opportunities. Parties with strong agrobiotechnological industries, such as Argentina, Brazil, or Canada, but also parties with vested stakes in genetic biocontrol, such as Australia and New Zealand, broadly prefer either a stronger focus on the potential sustainability benefits of synthetic biology, or to drop the discussion from the agenda altogether. The main advocate for a precautionary approach to synthetic biology is the European Union, partially supported by the African Group, although several African countries increasingly focus on the potential benefits of synthetic biology for disease vector control.

The complexity of this political landscape is further increased by the procedural separation of digital sequence information from the CBD's discussions on synthetic biology. As noted in part 2 above, digitalization, machine learning, and AI are central elements of synthetic biology. Yet the CBD addresses questions of Access and Benefit-sharing (ABS) in association with digital sequence information separately from the implications of synthetic biology for environmental modification and potential adverse impacts. It is in this ABS discussion that we can see a more traditional North-South division, where

developing countries have long pushed for an international mechanism that would distribute fairly and equitably the benefits that are generated from the biotechnological utilization of digital sequence information. Conversely, the Global North, including the European Union and its member states, have historically been wary of accepting any robust international regulatory mechanism that could turn out to be very costly for their domestic industries. While the European Union has in the past frequently demonstrated its willingness to compromise on ABS to achieve broader political goals (Oberthür and Rabitz 2014), it has been significantly less ambitious on the matter of digital sequence information than on the issue of precautionary regulation and forward-looking governance for the immediate environmental implications of synthetic biology.

At the time of writing, the CBD's 16th Conference of the Parties has adopted a milestone agreement on digital sequence information. In its decision 16/2 from November 2024, the Conference of the Parties has decided to create a multilateral mechanism that would receive voluntary payments from large commercial users of digital sequence information. The mechanism would then channel these payments into projects supporting the implementation of the CBD, particularly in the Global South (CBD 2024a). While non-binding and voluntary in nature, it is conceivable that some parties to the CBD, including the European Union and its member states, could adopt more robust domestic regulation for enhancing the implementation of decision 16/2. While it is still too early to assess its trajectory, the adoption of

decision 16/2 is, in itself, a major political breakthrough at a time when progress on other critical agenda items under the CBD, notably on the financial mechanism and resource mobilization, is facing significant hurdles.

The CBD's process on the synthetic biology track is presently significantly more fraught. In 2022, the Conference of the Parties adopted a decision towards the broad and regular horizon scanning, monitoring, and assessment of synthetic biology (CBD 2022b). The rationale behind this approach was that the CBD should possess ways and means of tracking the fast-moving field of synthetic biology to provide robust and timely advice and information to the parties, both in regard to potential opportunities as well as potential risks associated with technological change. During the 2022-2024 intersessional, a technical expert group developed a methodology geared towards this end, and identified an initial set of applications as potential priorities for the parties, including gene drive systems, self-spreading vaccines for wildlife, and the convergence between synthetic biology, machine learning, and AI. Significant pushback at the 16th Conference of the Parties, primarily from Argentina, Australia, Brazil, Canada, Japan, and New Zealand, led to this process largely being discontinued. What remains for the moment is an intersessional process heavily biased towards capacity building and the potential positive impacts of synthetic biology, while precaution and risk governance do not play a significant role any longer.

Synthetic biology under the CBD, both with its immediate environmental implications and in regard to the

utilization of digital sequence information in advanced AI models and other machine learning applications, remains a moving target. At the same time, rule development under the CBD remains incommensurate with the pace with which the technological field is evolving. This holds regardless of whether the potential benefits or the potential risks of synthetic biology should receive political priority: Neither does the CBD provide adequate rules for capitalizing on potential benefits for the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity, nor does it contribute to the robust and precautionary regulation of its potential risks. While there has been more progress on synthetic biology in regard to the CBD's benefit-sharing objective, decision 16/2 by itself does not address the underlying problem that large commercial users of digital sequence information have little to no economic incentives to divert parts of their profits into a multilateral fund for strengthening global biodiversity protection. One way or another, there is a need to develop international rules, under the CBD or elsewhere, to come to terms with the broad implications, positive and negative alike, that synthetic biology has for global environmental governance and for sustainable development more broadly.

5. Towards forward-looking global governance

Dealing with a fast-moving technological field where stakeholders disagree on whether international institutions should facilitate

development, diffusion, and uptake, or whether they should regulate, restrict, and prohibit, is a complex challenge. Where the use of digital sequence information in advanced AI applications is concerned, an additional problem is how to ensure adequate levels of fairness and equity when it comes to the *distribution* of benefits without, at the same time, hampering their *production* in the first place. This particularly applies to non-commercial uses of digital sequence information in applications of synthetic biology. In the past, international ABS discussions have tended to overestimate the financial resources that could be diverted from commercial uses of genetic resources, while underestimating the public good nature of non-commercial research that develops useful knowledge accessible, in principle, by everyone. While the contemporary development of AI models is overwhelmingly driven by Big Tech rather than non-commercial public researchers, there might be a risk of overregulating the field to the extent where basic research is negatively affected. Where novel biocontrol agents are concerned, the core problem is disagreement on whether biosafety and other risks outweigh the potential sustainability benefits, or whether these applications are, at best, dangerous distractions. Profound uncertainties as well as diverging interests and world views could well make fair, effective, and multilateral solutions elusive. All the while, technological progress makes it ever more urgent that *some* solution, and preferably the correct one, is found.

For technological fields such as synthetic biology, it is perhaps easier to define broad procedural parameters

that could guide the future development of substantive rules. If it is not possible to create robust international regulation in the present, due to political infeasibility and epistemic constraints, a second-best solution is to enhance the political processes that might lead to the adoption of such regulation in the future. At the very least, this requires international mechanisms for monitoring technological development and for identifying, as early as possible, frontier technologies with significant positive or negative implications for global sustainability, without biasing eventual regulatory choices. And while there may be reasonable disagreement on the precise regulatory implications of the precautionary principle (e.g. Sandin 1999), it is also clear that there are technological fat-tail risks that require appropriate assessment methods and management strategies. This includes, for instance, a hypothetical uncontrollable environmental diffusion of gene drive systems in off-target species, or risks associated with genetic hallucinations in AI-designed GMOs intended for environmental release. As many applications of synthetic biology are bound to be used in developing countries, where domestic capacities for monitoring and regulation may be limited, there is thus a strong rationale for intensifying the development of international standards, and guidance, on risk assessment and management. This, in turn, requires stronger institutionalization of scientific and technical advice in international decision-making processes.

There may also be a need for an international transparency mechanism that would make (non-sensitive) information available to the public about which applications of synthetic biology

are being developed, where, and for what purposes. Mistrust in the motives of synthetic biology developers and funding agencies is partially driven by the limited geographic and organizational diversity, with the US and a handful of other countries playing outsized roles, and with military funding possibly playing a significant role (Reeves et al. 2018; Rabitz 2024b). Concerns over transparency have been identified as a crucial factor in the governance of research on other controversial and high-risk technological fields (Talati et al. 2025). In principle, a transparency mechanism could help build public trust and contribute to better-informed decision-making processes.

A transparency mechanism could also contribute to the solution of another problem in the development of synthetic biology: the tendency for developers to site potentially hazardous activities in jurisdictions where domestic regulation is comparatively lenient. A particular focus of gene drive developers, for instance, is in Burkina Faso, where gene drives might provide a potential solution for Malaria vector control (see Hartley et al. 2021). Yet it is quite clear that jurisdictions characterized by endemic political instability, corruption, and an almost complete absence of the rule of law have limited capacities for adequately assessing and managing the risks associated with new and highly experimental types of GMOs. For synthetic biology developers, this is perhaps more than convenient, considering that the chances of obtaining regulatory approval for environmental releases of gene drive systems and similar GMOs within, say, the European Union are virtually zero.

Some form of international rules, or at least international political engagement, is thus necessary to address potential jurisdiction shopping and to prevent developers from siting projects in countries that can neither properly assess nor manage the associated risks.

6. Conclusions

Technological development commonly outpaces the adaptive capacities of regulatory institutions. International rules, on issues from nuclear energy over nanotechnology up to space traffic management, can take years or even decades to develop. And once such rules are in place, they tend to mirror the informal practices that have emerged in wider socio-technical systems in the meantime. As technologies consolidate themselves, they increasingly shape and restrict later regulatory choices (Rabitz 2025). The consequence is that the discretion that decision-makers may initially enjoy in the design of international regulatory mechanisms gradually dissipates. As time passes, political options diminish. The wait-and-see approach, in other words, does not fly for global technology governance. This does not necessarily mean that early regulatory action is required. But what is needed is a mode of doing international public policy that is more systematically oriented towards the future than is commonly the case.

Scholars are increasingly aware of the need for anticipation and foresight in governance choices (see Vervoort and Gupta 2018; Hale 2024). International organizations, from the World Health

Organization over the World Economic Forum up to the CBD are increasingly adopting foresight methods, including horizon scans, as ways of providing decision-relevant information on governance challenges that operate on multi-decadal timescales. Synthetic biology, as a technological field that enables an unprecedented depth of intervention into living systems, and that is recently merging with AI as one of the defining technologies of the 21st century, poses exactly such a challenge. Crucially, this means that the international political process must adopt a longer view beyond the conventional day-to-day bargaining: One useful way of doing so would be a long-term political commitment, for instance in the form of a decision by the Conference of the Parties to the CBD, towards the safe, sustainable, and equitable use of synthetic biology in the context of global biodiversity governance, without specifying whether international rules subsequently adopted towards that end would tend more towards restriction or towards facilitation. Robust international rules based on core principles of equity, sustainability, and safety are necessary regardless of whether synthetic biology is part of the solution to the global environmental crisis, or whether it is rather part of the problem.

While there is a need for the systematic generation of expert knowledge on novel technological challenges and opportunities, the experience with the CBD's 16th Conference of the Parties shows how systematic foresight was sacrificed on the altar of political expediency. The shift from an intersessional process geared towards horizon scanning, monitoring, and assessment, to a process that

predominantly aims at capacity-building for synthetic biology, is unfortunate. Governments and other stakeholders critically depend on high-quality information in fast-moving and uncertain technological fields such as synthetic biology. This applies particularly to developing countries with limited domestic capacities for generating such information by themselves. International foresight can thus also help to alleviate the information asymmetry that frequently plagues multilateral negotiations on technological and environmental matters. The key challenge, then, is how to design foresight mechanisms in such a way that they receive sufficient levels of support from the countries of the Global South to be viable in contexts such as the CBD, where a small number of countries continues to oppose horizon scanning, monitoring, and assessment due to concerns that this might pave the way towards restrictive international regulation. Yet while more and better information does not necessarily lead to better international rules, it is inconceivable how the global implications of synthetic biology could be managed in fair and effective ways without one or the other international foresight mechanism.

The recent return of a Trump administration in the US does generally not bode well for the prospects of responsible global governance of synthetic biology. The revocation by Trump of a 2023 executive order on AI safety likely indicates a commitment towards unhampered technology development without adequate consideration of risks and risk management. As the US is not a party to the CBD and its Cartagena Protocol, it remains outside of the ambit of the

(limited) rules that have been developed on synthetic biology in that context over the past two decades. At the same time, the Trump administration has notified its intent to pull the US out of the World Health Organization, where some specific sets of rules and guidelines address digital sequence information on pandemic influenza viruses, genetically-modified insects, and other items relevant to synthetic biology. Together with the wider disruptions that the second Trump administration is likely to cause to multilateralism as such, the challenges posed by synthetic biology have only increased with the presidential transition in the US.

Policy recommendations

- The European Union should seek closer ties with developing countries to create a global mechanism for tracking technology development in synthetic biology.
- The integration of synthetic biology and AI poses considerable biosafety and biosecurity challenges that require strengthened oversight in the appropriate international forums, including the World Health Organization and the Biological Weapons Convention.
- Governments may wish to consider a formal moratorium on the development of high-risk genetic biocontrol agents that are unlikely to qualify for environmental release in a manner consistent with the precautionary principle.
- The scientific community should use all the tools at its disposal, including terms of service and similar private law contractual arrangements, to

prevent public genetic sequence
databases from being used as

training sets for proprietary AI
models.

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